

ILUS Zenodo Community Repository

How to upload guidance

2023 release features: <https://blog.zenodo.org/2023/10/13/2023-10-13-zenodo-rdm/>

ILUS Zenodo Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/ilus>

Zenodo is a free-of-use general-purpose research output repository. It is designed for long-term archiving (at least 20 years). The ILUS Zenodo Community filters and curates the various Zenodo research outputs in a centralised way. It allows sharing Open Access research outputs with a persistent identifier (DOI).

Upload of Posters and Presentations

1. Approval checklist

Authors check the content of the presentation files or posters (PPTX or PDF):

- Do you have the appropriate rights of use/publication for the content presented?
- Have the rights of third parties been taken into account?
- Are the (image) sources indicated?
- Does the Poster or Slides contain the name of the author?

2. Save the uploads as PDF

Important:

- Once an upload is published, it cannot be removed. It is persistently archived.
- However, the metadata can be changed and edited at any time.
- Each new version (upload) will obtain a new DOI.
- Zenodo always provides an overarching DOI that cites all the versions and resolves the latest version by clicking on it.

Many thanks from the ILUS-Teams

Get started!

1

New upload

Drag and drop files

OR

Upload files

2

Select the community where you want to submit your record.

Select a community

Click on **Select a community**

Select a community

All

My communities

ILUS

Type **ILUS**

ILUS - International Land Use Symposium [↗](#)

The biennial International Land Use Symposium b...

Event

Owner

Select

Click **Select** to accept this Community

Click **NO** if you don't have a DOI. Otherwise, click **YES** to add the existing DOI for the upload. **Zenodo provides two DOIs**. One which belongs to the specific version, together with an overarching DOI number. For example, the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7112779 has the following overarching DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7112778. New versions generate a new DOI. The overarching DOI number always resolves the latest version.

Digital Object Identifier *

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

Copy/paste your existing DOI here:

Get a DOI now!

Option to **reserve a DOI** before publishing it.

Reserve a DOI by pressing the button (so it can be included in files prior to upload). The DOI is registered when your upload is published.

Select the **upload type** (e.g. Data, Software, Presentation, Preprint etc.).

Resource type *

Fill in your upload title.

Title *

Additional title *

Type *

Language

Alternative title

Select language

Add titles or subtitles. You can set multiple languages to the titles or subtitles.

+ Add titles

Publication date *

2023-10-25

Set the publication date.

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Creators

+ Add creator

Add creator

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name* Given names

Identifiers
e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations
Search or create affiliation

Role
Select role

Cancel Save and add another Save

Add the upload Creators.

Search for your name, otherwise add it manually.

Add First name here

Add manually your Surname and name.

Add your ORCID or ISNI, GND identifier.

IMPORTANT: Search for YOUR Affiliation. It should appear automatically. If not type your affiliation manually.

Add your role.

Della Chiesa, Stefano¹

 Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

IMPORTANT: At the preview phase or once published, **click show affiliations** and **check that YOUR affiliation appears with the ROR logo identifier.** It won't appear if your affiliation doesn't have a ROR identifier or if you added your affiliation manually.

Fill in a brief **description/abstract of the upload.**

Add an additional description if desired.

Choose Open Access as publication policy with CC BY License. It means the upload is freely available and usable with the single constraint of crediting/citing/acknowledging the source. You can choose from other standard licenses or add a custom one. Please, be aware that only CC-BY and CC0 are

Description

Paragraph **B** *I*

+ Add description

Licenses

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work provided the original creator is credited. [Read more](#)

+ Add standard + Add custom

Fill in authors' names, their affiliation and ORCID if available.

Contributors

+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects

Suggest from: All

Languages

Dates

Date *	Type *	Description
<input type="text" value="YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

Add the necessary keywords. It helps find uploads and filter them (e.g. by a project).

Add the mandatory Keyword: "ILUS 2023"

Primary language of your document/upload.

Add if applicable date of Submission/Acceptance/Etc.

Add version by typing e.g. **1.0** for the first version. Or **2.0** for the second version. For minor changes you might adopt for example **1.1**, or **2.1**.

Funding

Zenodo lists a few major funding agencies. It is not a comprehensive list. If you find your funder add it and specify the grant number. You might select existing funding **or add your custom one.**

Awards

+ Add award + Add custom

Some uploads are related to others. For example, a publication is associated with a dataset, an algorithm, documentation, a report, a presentation, etc. You **enhance the visibility of all the research outputs by listing the corresponding identifier** (using its Persistent Identifier, e.g. DOI).

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
Select relation... ▾	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/> ▾	<input type="text"/> ▾

+ Add related work

Zenodo allows to list some references. Put the whole reference string.

References

Reference string *

+ Add reference

You can add the journal details. It is generally used when the upload is published on a journal. Zenodo allows to upload existing publication with their own DOI.

Journal

Title

Title of the journal on which the article was published

ISSN

International Standard Serial Number

Volume **Issue** **Pages**

Imprint

Book title

Title of the book or report which this upload is part of.

ISBN

International Standard Book Number

Place **Pages**
Place where the imprint was published

Thesis

Awarding university

You can add Metadata info about a conference related to the upload. It is frequent when you upload a poster or conference presentation.

Conference

Title **Acronym**

Place **Dates**

Location where the conference took place

Website

Session **Part**

Session within the conference. Part within the session.

ILUS 2023 – International Land Use Symposium

ILUS 2023

Ahmedabad, India

4-6 October 2023

https://ilus2023.ioer.info/

If applicable, add the session

If applicable, add the Part

Draft ⓘ

Save draft Preview

Publish

Visibility*

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Delete

Save the uploaded draft and, review it using the preview feature. If you are satisfied, click publish. **Be aware that published output cannot be undone or withdrawn.**

Choose Restricted Access to set access and usage constraints conditions. Users can see only the metadata.

Choose Embargoed Access to make the upload available after a specific date. Embargo is enabled by selecting restricted.

Communities

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

- + Submit to community
- 🗨 Pending submissions
- ⚙ Manage communities

You can submit the upload to one or multiple Communities at the preview phase or once published. You can view any pending submission or manage them.